

Asymmetric syntheses of unsaturated amino acids and peptides via chelate-enolate Claisen rearrangements[†]

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N-Protected amino acid allylic esters can easily be deprotonated by LDA at -78° and transmetalated by addition of metal salts. Upon warming up to room temperature, these enolates undergo Claisen rearrangements giving rise to unsaturated amino acids. Starting from chiral allylic alcohols, optically active amino acids are obtained. This chirality transfer can also be used for stereoselective peptide modifications. If tosylated peptide allylic esters are subjected to Claisen rearrangement, the chirality of the peptide chain can also be used as a stereocontrolling element. Another possibility to introduce chirality is given by the rearrangement in the presence of chiral ligands, such as *Chinchona* alkaloids.

Amino acids are one of the five major classes of natural products and they exhibit important and diverse biological functions. Besides their role as constituents of peptides, proteins and peptidoglycans, amino acids have also a function for neuronal signal transduction and as precursor for further metabolic products. Unusual structures are mainly produced by microorganisms and have evolved to interfere with biochemical pathways of other organisms. Many of these unusual amino acids show antibiotic activity and several man-designed derivatives find pharmaceutical applications. Therefore various different approaches towards this important class of compounds have been developed during the last decades¹.

γ,δ -Unsaturated amino acids are one group of unnatural amino acids with certain significance, not only as naturally occurring non-proteinogenic amino acids such as the isoleucine antagonist cyclopentenylglycine² and the antibiotic furanomycin³, but also as important intermediates for the synthesis of complex amino acids⁴. Besides the *N*-

sulfonylimine ene reaction⁵ and the nucleophilic allylation of glycine cation equivalents⁶, the sigmatropic rearrangement processes are suited for the introduction of the unsaturated side-chains as well⁷.

Reactions of chelated amino acid ester enolates

For some time our group is interested in reactions of chelated enolates such as **1**⁸. These enolates can easily be obtained from protected amino acid esters (PG: protecting group) via deprotonation with LDA or LHMDS and subsequent transmetalation by addition of metal salts (MX_n). The chelated enolates can be trapped with electrophiles such as aldehydes or ketones, giving rise to the corresponding aldol products. On the other hand, if allylic esters are used, warming the enolates to room temperature results in a Claisen rearrangement, providing γ,δ -unsaturated amino acids (Scheme 1). These chelated enolates have several advantages in comparison to their non-chelated analogs:

Scheme 1. Reactions of chelated amino acid ester enolates **1**

[†]Dedicated to Professor D. Nasipuri on the occasion of his 75th birthday

(a) Because of the fixed enolate geometry by chelation, many reactions of these enolates proceed with a high degree of diastereoselectivity. For example, aldol reactions of **1** with various aldehydes in the presence of titanium or zinc salts occur in a highly diastereoselective fashion, whereas the corresponding lithium enolates show only modest selectivity⁹.

(b) The chelated enolates are significantly more stable than the corresponding, probably non-chelated, lithium enolates. In contrast to these, the chelate enolates can be warmed to room temperature without decomposition. This allows the expansion of the field of enolate chemistry to reactions, such as Claisen rearrangements¹⁰ or palladium catalyzed allylic alkylations¹¹, which in general can not be carried out with *normal*, non-stabilized enolates.

(c) Many manipulations on enolates such as **1** are possible. Besides variations of the protecting group, an excessive *metal tuning* should allow the modification of the reactivity and selectivity of these enolates. Because, in most cases, the coordination sphere of the metal ion M is not saturated in the bidentate enolate complex, the additional coordination of chiral ligands on the chelated metal is possible¹².

Chelate-enolate Claisen rearrangements

Recently, we have developed a new variation of the ester enolate Claisen rearrangement proceeding via these chelated allylic ester enolates (Scheme 1). Due to the fixed enolate geometry, as a result of chelate formation, the rearrangement proceeds with a high degree of diastereoselectivity (>93% ds) and is independent of the substitution pattern and the protecting groups PG used. The formation of the *syn*-product can be explained by a preferential rearrangement via the chair-like transition state¹³. This protocol is suitable for the synthesis of various types of amino acids (Scheme 2).

Besides *E*-configured esters also the *Z*-isomers can be used¹⁴, including cyclic structures such as cycloalkenyl glycinates **2** (Scheme 3)¹⁵. These substrates are of special interest, not only because of the biological activity of the resulting amino acids, but also because it is known that cyclic allylic esters prefer to rearrange via the *boat like* transition state. This is also the case with these chelated enolates, and rearrangement of the *Z*-configured **2** gives rise to the *syn*-products³.

Based on the high reactivity of the chelated enolates the rearrangement is also suitable for the synthesis of sterically highly demanding amino acids containing quaternary carbon centers¹⁶. Amino acids containing quaternary β -carbon

Scheme 2. Applications of chelate-enolate Claisen rearrangements

Scheme 3. Claisen rearrangements of chiral allylic esters

centres are, in addition to α -alkylated amino acids, an especially interesting class of nonproteinogenic amino acids. The most common representative, *tert*-leucine, occurs as a building block in various complex natural products¹⁷. The α -alkylated amino acids are especially interesting with respect

to their activity as enzyme inhibitors¹⁸. Both types of amino acids can be obtained, depending on the substitution pattern of the allylic esters.

If unsymmetrically substituted esters **4** ($R^1 \neq R^2 \neq H$) are used, the β -quarternary amino acids **5** can be obtained in a highly stereoselective fashion. Switching from glycine esters to allylic esters of other amino acids ($R^3 \neq H$) allows the synthesis of α -alkylated amino acids¹⁹. With highly substituted esters ($R^1 \neq R^2 \neq R^3 \neq H$) even amino acids with two adjacent quarternary centers can be obtained.

α -Allenic α -amino acids are attractive candidates for the specific inhibition of vitamin B₆ linked decarboxylases²⁰, e.g. α -allenyl DOPA rapidly inactivates porcine kidney aromatic group amino acid decarboxylase²¹. Despite their potential as 'mechanism-based' inhibitors, not many syntheses of α -allenic amino acids are described in the literature so far²². Therefore we investigated the chelate-enolate Claisen rearrangement of various propargylic esters **6** for the syntheses of these very sensitive amino acids **7**²³. As in the allylic ester rearrangement, ZnCl₂ gives the best results, no dependence on the *N*-protecting group is observed, and the *syn*-product²⁴ is formed preferentially.

Allylic esters are slightly more reactive in comparison to propargylic esters and therefore rearrangement of amino acid esters of enynols **8** results in the chemoselective formation of amino acids **9** with conjugated enyne side-chains²⁵. Best results are obtained with LHMDS as a base, and because of the high reactivity of the enolates formed, the reaction proceeds already at -78° , and therefore the addition of ZnCl₂ is not necessary with these substrates.

Asymmetric Claisen rearrangements

As illustrated, it is possible to carry out the ester enolate Claisen rearrangement in a highly diastereoselective fashion via control of the enolate geometry. Although from a synthetic point of view, the generation of racemic products is not fully satisfying. For an application to amino acid synthesis, it is important not only to control the *relative*, but also the *absolute* configuration of the stereogenic centers²⁶. Therefore we investigated three different approaches to solve this problem (Fig. 1).

(i) The *classical* approach for the introduction of chirality is the rearrangement of chiral allylic esters. Due to the concerted, suprafacial nature of the Claisen rearrangement, the degree of 1,3-chirality is often >90% to nearly quantitative¹³. If esters of chiral allylic alcohols are used, chirality transfer occurs also to the α -position of the carboxylic acid subunit. Therefore this approach is used very often in the asymmetric synthesis of various types of natural products.

Figure 1. Asymmetric chelate-enolate Claisen rearrangements.

(ii) Another possibility is the introduction of chirality on the amino terminus of the amino acid ester. The easiest way to do so is the incorporation of the amino acid allylic ester onto a peptide chain. We were mainly interested to see if it is possible to carry out the rearrangement also with complex substrates like peptides as well, and if it is possible to transfer the chirality of the peptide chain somehow to the new chiral centers formed during the rearrangement process.

(iii) If these chelate bridged species really exist, as we assume, there should be at least some induction if the reaction is carried out in the presence of chiral ligands. In contrast to many other *auxiliary-directed* asymmetric syntheses, in this case the chiral information is bound temporarily by coordination, and therefore this approach is the most attractive one, especially if the ligand can easily be recovered after the reaction.

Rearrangements of chiral allylic esters

This most commonly used approach for asymmetric Claisen rearrangements can also be applied in amino acid synthesis (Scheme 3). Chiral allylic alcohols can easily be obtained from chiral pool materials²⁷ or using enzymatic techniques²⁸. Because of our interest in the synthesis of polyhydroxylated amino acids, we investigated the rearrangement of chiral allylic esters, easily obtained from tartaric acid or sugars²⁹. As expected, the rearrangement of **10** occurred with a high degree of chirality transfer, giving rise to optically active amino acid **11**, which can be used as precursors for the synthesis of polyhydroxylated piperidine alkaloids such as **12**³⁰. Another interesting example was described recently by Hudlicky *et al.* in connection with a morphine synthesis³¹. The required allylic ester **13** was obtained via enzymatic oxidation of the corresponding aromatic system³² and subsequent esterification.

Claisen rearrangements of peptides

Peptides and cyclopeptides containing unnatural amino acids are quite common in nature, often found in marine organisms³³. Many of these peptides show antibiotic activity³⁴, and are therefore highly interesting from a pharma-

ceptical point of view³⁵. For straightforward approaches towards these targets and efficient target screenings, flexible synthetic concepts are necessary. Besides the classical peptide couplings of commercial available or synthesized amino acids, especially the modification of existing peptides is suitable for this purpose. These modifications can be carried out in the side-chain or directly on the peptide backbone³⁶. The great advantage of side-chain modifications results from the fact that the chiral center in the newly formed amino acid can be taken over from the precursor amino acid³⁷. On the other hand, suitable precursors are necessary. In contrast, achiral glycine subunits can be used for backbone modifications, because the whole side-chain is transferred. As reactive intermediates glycine cation equivalents³⁸ as well as glycine anions (glycine enolates) can be used³⁹. The major drawback of this concept results from the difficulty to control the stereochemical outcome of the C-C coupling step.

Therefore we focused mainly on the following question: Is it possible to transfer the chiral information from the peptide chain to the new chiral center formed during the rearrangement process, probably via some peptide metal enolate complexes?

As a first example, we investigated the rearrangement of allylic ester **15** in the presence of zinc chloride (Scheme 4)⁴⁰. Subsequent esterification of the rearrangement product with diazomethane resulted in the formation of unsaturated dipeptide **16** in only moderate yield (28%) and without significant selectivity. Therefore we were interested at this point to find a possibility to catalyze this reaction. Since the tremendous work done by Overman on rearrangement catalysis,⁴¹ many applications, especially of Pd^{II}-catalyzed rear-

Scheme 4. Peptide Claisen rearrangements.

rangements, are described in the literature. In our case, addition of 10 mol% Pd^{II} resulted in a decrease in yield (20%) without affecting the stereoselectivity. Because Pd^{II} is known to form stable complexes with peptides⁴², the formation of a less reactive palladium enolate, which does not rearrange, is probable. In contrast, Pd⁰ (10 mol%) catalyzed the reaction in the expected manner, and the desired product was obtained in excellent yield (85%). But under these conditions, the allylic amino acid was obtained not via Claisen rearrangement, but an intermolecular palladium-catalyzed allylic alkylation. As for example, rearrangement of the crotyl ester **17** resulted not only in the formation of the expected 'rearrangement product' **18**, the amino acid with a linear side-chain **19** was formed in a comparable amount. This fact, as well as the nearly complete lack of diastereoselectivity in the newly generated amino acid of **18** (*syn* : *anti* 2 : 1) is a clear indication for a π -allylpalladium intermediate.

Although the application of palladium catalysts resulted in an increase of yield, it was also responsible for an decrease of selectivity, regio- and diastereoselectivity as well. Therefore we undertook an intensive metal tuning to find suitable chelate complexes which undergo Claisen rearrangement without assistance of a palladium catalyst. By far the best results are obtained if manganese salts are used for chelation (Scheme 5)⁴³. Independent of the protecting groups (PG) used, the yields obtained with these manganese enolates were always excellent (78–98%), with esters of terminal allylic alcohols and with *trans*-configured substituted alcohols as well. These are especially interesting, because in their rearrangement two new stereogenic centers are formed. In all examples investigated so far, the simple diastereoselectivity of the rearrangement was very high ($\geq 95\%$) and comparable to the results obtained with amino acids. This protocol is also suitable for the direct introduction of α -alkylated amino acids into peptides (**21**, R \neq H). These derivatives show higher resistances towards proteases, and therefore they are interesting for the development of peptide-based pharmaceuticals.

Scheme 5. Peptide Claisen rearrangements using Mn-enolates.

No significant induced diastereoselectivity was observed. Obviously the *N*-terminal amino acid has no notable influence on the rearrangement. This is also reflected in the high yields obtained, which are also nearly independent of the peptide used. Because the influence of the adjacent amino acid on the rearrangement can be neglected, this allows for the stereoselective synthesis of peptides if esters of chiral allylic alcohols such as **22** are used. The corresponding dipeptides **23** were obtained not only in good to excellent yields but also in a highly diastereoselective fashion. These unsaturated peptides are now suitable substrates for subsequent reactions on the double bond (side-chain modifications).

Using these manganese enolates, the chirality is transferred from the chiral ester moiety towards the peptide backbone. The good results obtained are highly satisfying and are the base for further interesting applications. But to be honest, it was not exactly what we were looking for: our aim was to transfer the chirality from the peptide backbone to the new chiral center of the *C*-terminal amino acid. We were interested to see if it is possible to coordinate a deprotonated peptide chain not only twice (like amino acid ester enolates) but several times towards the chelating metal. We hoped to obtain peptide metal complexes in which one face of the enolate is shielded by the complex. Although manganese chloride obviously is not the best choice, other metal salts could be more suitable for this purpose. Therefore, we investigated the rearrangement of several dipeptide crotyl esters **20** (Scheme 5, R' = H)⁴⁴. The results obtained are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Chelate Claisen rearrangement of dipeptide allylic esters **20**

Substrate	PG	R	MX _n	Yield %	% ds
20a	Boc	Bn	Ti(O ^{<i>i</i>} Pr) ₄	57	82
20a	Boc	Bn	NiCl ₂	86	77
20b	Boc	<i>i</i> Pr	Ti(O ^{<i>i</i>} Pr) ₄	65	89
20b	Boc	<i>i</i> Pr	NiCl ₂	69	81
20b	Boc	<i>i</i> Pr	CuBr	78	78
20c	Ts	<i>i</i> Pr	Ti(O ^{<i>i</i>} Pr) ₄	60	96
20c	Ts	<i>i</i> Pr	NiCl ₂	66	93
20c	Ts	<i>i</i> Pr	–	55	92

Starting with the Boc-protected phenylalanine derivative **20a**, we found good selectivities in the presence of Ti(O^{*i*}Pr)₄ and NiCl₂ as well. Although the selectivity observed in the presence of NiCl₂ was a little lower, the yield was much better. Replacing phenylalanine by the sterically more bulky valine (**20b**) resulted in an increase of selectivity. Other metal salts such as CuBr gave comparable re-

sults. Switching to other carbamate protecting groups like *Z* had no significant effect on the diastereoselectivity (ds). Introduction of the tosyl group (**20c**) however increased the ds from 89 to 96%. Tosyl protected peptides are therefore the substrates of choice; in all examples investigated so far, the selectivities were in the range 90–96 ds, with yields up to 90%.

Most surprising was the fact that even the lithium enolates showed these excellent results. This is in sharp contrast to our observations with amino acid esters. In general, the chelate Claisen rearrangement takes place during the warm up at about –20°, and lithium enolates normally decompose before they reach this rearrangement temperature. Presumably this is not the case with tosylated peptides. This can probably be explained by the formation of lithium complexes³⁶, which have a stabilizing effect comparable to the chelate formation with other metal salts. This may also explain the *unlike*⁴⁵ (*S*/*R*) diastereoselectivities observed. In all examples investigated so far, an (*R*)-amino acid was formed during the Claisen rearrangement, if an (*S*)-amino acid was placed in the peptide chain.

For the reactions with NiCl₂, this stereochemical outcome can be rationalized by the formation of a square-planar chelate complex (Fig. 2), in which one face of the enolate is shielded by the *R* side-chain of the (*S*)-amino acid. The rearrangement occurs on the sterically less hindered opposite (*unlike*) face of the enolate, giving rise to the (*R*)-amino acid. This rational can also explain the excellent selectivities obtained with the sterically most demanding amino acids, valine and isoleucine. Similar complexes are probably involved in rearrangements of other metal enolates, including lithium enolates.

Figure 2. Metal peptide complex.

If this assumption is correct, one might expect an induction not only from amino acids adjacent to the *C*-terminal amino acid like in the investigated dipeptides, but also from amino acids 'further away' in the peptide chain, e.g. in tri- or tetrapeptides. Therefore we investigated the rearrangement of several allylic esters such as **24** containing valine as a stereocontrolling element (Scheme 6). In contrast to the results obtained in the rearrangement of dipeptides, lithium enolates showed no significant diastereoselectivity. Tin chlo-

Scheme 6. Rearrangements of *N*-tosylated peptides.

ride is the chelating agent of choice for the rearrangement of these larger peptides. The tosyl protected derivatives gave excellent yields and also very high diastereoselectivities. This is quite surprising with respect to the fact that five atoms are in between the stereocontrolling valine and the newly formed chiral center of the *C*-terminal amino acid. Even increasing the distance to six atoms by incorporation of β -amino acid had no significant negative influence on the rearrangement. On the other hand, attempts to increase the diastereoselectivity by introduction of a second chiral amino acid into the peptide chain were unsuccessful. Obviously the side-chains of these amino acids interact with each other in such a way that the overall shielding effect of these side-chains is not increased in comparison to the single side-chains. The selectivities obtained are not limited to tosylated tripeptides, comparable results are also obtained with Boc protected derivatives, although the yields are lower in these cases.

Incorporation of secondary amino acids, such as sarcosine or proline, into the peptide chain should interrupt the successive coordination of the peptide chain towards the chelating metal ion. Therefore, one might expect and does observe a dramatic drop in the selectivity obtained with these derivatives. Rearrangement of tetrapeptide **26** gave high yields of the expected amino acid **27** as a nearly 1 : 1 diastereomeric mixture, independent whether SnCl_2 was present in the solution.

Claisen rearrangements in the presence of chiral ligands

Besides the described substrate controlled asymmetric rearrangements, we also focused on rearrangements in the presence of chiral ligands. This approach is of special interest because not many examples of asymmetric rearrangements of this type are described in the literature so far. The first rearrangements in the presence of chiral Lewis acids were reported by Yamamoto *et al.*⁴⁶, while the first ester enolate rearrangement, proceeding via chiral boron-enolates, was described by Corey *et al.*⁴⁷. Both procedures need at

least equimolar amounts of the chiral auxiliary. Very recently Overman *et al.*⁴⁸ reported for the first time a catalytic asymmetric version of the allyl imidate rearrangement in the presence of chiral Pd^{II} -complexes.

In view of the many different metal salts which can be used in the chelate-enolate rearrangement, and the even higher number of chiral ligands which are commonly used in asymmetric synthesis, we undertook an intensive metal and ligand screening. As a model reaction we investigated the rearrangement of TFA-protected glycine crotyl ester **28** (Scheme 7)¹². The crotyl ester was chosen because the rearrangement provides the corresponding dehydroisoleucine derivative or the *allo*-isomer **29**, respectively, as the major product. The TFA-protecting group allows the GC-analytical determination of the absolute configuration of the rearrangement product after hydrogenation and by comparison with the naturally occurring isoleucine derivatives.

Scheme 7. Rearrangement in the presence of quinine.

A lot of variations were undertaken concerning the metal salts used for chelation. Zinc chloride, which normally gives the best results, provides the rearrangement product in excellent yields but with only moderate ee's. The metal salt of choice so far is aluminum isopropoxide ($\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3$).

Among the ligands investigated, the best results were obtained with amino alcohols. Diol- or diamino ligands which are frequently used in asymmetric catalysis⁴⁹ showed no significant induction (less than 5% ee), independent of the metal salt used. Simple amino alcohols, easily obtained by reduction of amino acids, are comparable to these ligands. Introduction of a second center of chirality (α to the OH group) resulted in a dramatical increase in the selectivity. The switch from the simple alcohols like valinol to the ephedra alkaloids results in an increase in enantioselectivity from 4 to 27% ee. The big advantage of these alkaloids is the possibility to generate both enantiomers of the amino acids, because both enantiomeric ligands are commercially available. The same is true with the Cinchona alkaloids, which are by far the ligands of choice. In this case excellent yields and diastereoselectivities are obtained (up to 98% each) as well as a very high induction (86% ee), especially if 2 to 2.5 equiv. of quinine are used. Unfortunately this excess of chiral ligand is necessary because the coordination of the ligand to the chelated metal decreases the reactivity of the enolae.

By using a significant excess of quinine, the concentration of ligand-free chelate enolate, which undergoes the rearrangement more easily, is diminished. The usage of an excess of quinine is unpleasant indeed, but acceptable, because it can easily be recovered (>95%) after the reaction by simple extraction with hydrochloric acid. On the other hand, quinine is commercially available, like the pseudoenantiomer quinidine, and can be used directly without purification. While (*R*)-amino acids are obtained in the presence of quinine, the isomeric quinidine gives rise to the corresponding (*S*)-amino acids. Fortunately the rearrangement can also be applied to highly substituted allylic esters providing quarternary amino acids⁵⁰.

Under the reaction conditions used, cinchona alkaloids probably bind as bidentate ligands to the chelated metal via the OH- and the tertiary *N*-functionality because alkylation or acylation of the alcohol moiety results in a dramatical decrease of the enantioselectivity (<5% ee). The asymmetric chelate enolate Claisen rearrangement can be applied to various types of substrates, while with *E*-configured allylic esters the enantioselectivities observed are always in the range between 80 and 90% ee (Scheme 7). The *syn*-configured products are formed preferentially and therefore this approach is especially suitable for the synthesis of *allo*-isoleucine and derivatives.

Based on this asymmetric chelate Claisen rearrangement we developed a short and very convenient synthesis of suitable protected isostatine **32**, with *de novo* generation of all stereogenic centers (Scheme 8)⁵¹. Starting from crude amino acid **29** the enantiomeric purity was increased by single crystallization with (*S*)-phenethylamine. For the prolongation of the carbon chain, a Claisen condensation via the corresponding imidazolide was chosen. Addition of the lithium enolate of benzyl acetate gave rise to β -ketoester **30**. The subsequent reduction with sodium borohydride should be carried out at low temperature, to avoid reductive cleavage of the TFA protecting group. The diastereoselectivity in the reduction step was very good (94% ds), and the amino acid **32** was obtained after catalytic hydrogenation. The free amino acid should be obtained by saponification or reduction of the protecting group. But even more interesting is the direct introduction of **32** into peptides by coupling with other amino acids. As for example, reaction with phenylalanine benzyl ester under assistance of TBTU⁵² gave rise to dipeptide **33**, which can selectively be prolonged on both sides, because of the orthogonality of the protecting groups.

Conclusion

N-Protected amino acid allylic esters can easily be

Scheme 8. Synthesis of isostatine derivatives.

deprotected by LDA at -78° and trans-metallated by addition of metal salts. Chelated metal enolates, which undergo Claisen rearrangements upon warming up to room temperature, giving rise to unsaturated amino acids, are formed with many different salts. Due to the fixed enolate geometry as a result of chelate formation, the rearrangement proceeds with a high degree of diastereoselectivity. This procedure can be applied to acyclic as well as to cyclic substrates and allows for the synthesis of amino acids containing quarternary carbon centers. Starting from chiral allylic alcohols, optically active amino acids are obtained. This chirality transfer can also be used for stereoselective peptide modifications. If tosylated peptide allylic esters are subjected towards Claisen rearrangement, the chirality of the peptide chain can also be used as a stereocontrolling element. Another possibility to introduce chirality is given by the rearrangement in the presence of chiral ligands. Best results so far are obtained if $\text{Al}(\text{O}^i\text{Pr})_3$ is used as the chelating metal salt and the Cinchona alkaloids as bidentate ligands. Quinine gives rise to (*2R*)-configured amino acids, while quinidine delivers the (*2S*)-derivatives in very high yields and excellent enantioselectivities (80–93% ee). Therefore this protocol can easily be applied to natural product synthesis.

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